

**Mixed-ligand complexes of Cobalt(III)
containing Trimethylenediamine and
Some Bidentate Ligands**

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THERE has been considerable interest on the syntheses and optical properties of mixed-ligand heterochelate complexes of cobalt(III) containing ethylenediamine and bidentate ligands¹. Very little has appeared on similar heterochelate complexes containing trimethylenediamine²⁻⁵. In this preliminary communication we report the syntheses of some new cobalt(III) heterochelates, the ligands used being trimethylenediamine, biguanide, picolinic acid, acetylacetone, acetoacetanilide, benzoylacetanilide and malonic acid.

Preparation of the complexes

A. For complexes with the ligands biguanide, picolinic acid, acetylacetone, acetoacetanilide and benzoylacetanilide—To an aqueous solution of *trans*-[CoCl₂(tn)₂]Cl (3.1 g, 0.01 mole in 20 ml) an aqueous or ethanolic solution of the appropriate ligand (0.01 mole) was added and the pH of the solution was adjusted to 7. In case of biguanide an aqueous neutralised solution of biguanide hydrochloride (2.3 g, 0.01 mole) was added to the *trans*-[CoCl₂(tn)₂]Cl solution (3.1 g, in 20 ml) which was previously neutralised to pH 7 with 2N NaOH. The mixture was heated on a steam bath for 2-3 hrs. The pH of the solution was finally adjusted to 6.5 with 2N HCl. This was cooled in ice for 1 hr. and the separated red precipitates were filtered, washed with ice-cold water followed by 95% ethanol. Water

followed by acetone was used for washing in case of acetoacetanilide and benzoylacetanilide complexes. The complexes were recrystallised from minimum amount of water and finally dried *in vacuo*. Yield = 30-50%.

B. [Co(mal)(tn)₂]Cl·3H₂O—To an aqueous solution of [Co(CO₃)(tn)₂]Cl·H₂O (3.2 g, 0.01 mole in 20 ml) an aqueous solution of malonic acid (1 g, 0.01 mole in 10 ml) was added. The mixture was heated on a steam bath for 1 hr. and was then concentrated to a small volume, and cooled in ice bath. The separated rose red precipitates were filtered, washed with ice-cold water followed by 95% ethanol, and dried *in vacuo*. Yield = 40%.

The analytical, conductance and electronic spectral data of the complexes are given in Table I.

The *trans*-dichlorobis(trimethylenediamine) cobalt(III) chloride or carbonatobis(trimethylenediamine) cobalt(III) chloride has been found to react with one molecule of chelating ligand such as biguanide, picolinic acid, acetylacetone, acetoacetanilide, benzoylacetanilide and malonic acid, resulting in the formation of cobalt(III) heterochelate complexes. The conductance measurements in aqueous medium indicate tri-univalent nature of [Co(bigH)(tn)₂]Cl₃, bi-univalent nature of [Co(pic)(tn)₂]Cl₂, [Co(acac)(tn)₂]Cl₂, [Co(acan)(tn)₂]Cl₂, [Co(benzan)(tn)₂]Cl₂, and uni-univalent nature of [Co(mal)(tn)₂]Cl (ref. 4). The room temperature magnetic susceptibility measurements by the Gouy method indicate that the complexes are diamagnetic. The magnetic data are indicative of octahedral structure of the complexes with d²sp³ bonding. The electronic spectra of the complexes exhibit one or two ligand field bands at around 20000 and 28000 cm⁻¹ typical of octahedral cobalt(III) complexes⁶. The second band cannot be located in some complexes as it is buried underneath the strong metal ligand charge transfer transitions.

The equivalent weights of the complexes were determined by running the aqueous solutions through H⁺ form of a cation exchange resin

TABLE—I. ANALYTICAL, CONDUCTANCE AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF COBALT(III) HETEROCHELATES^a

Complex	%Co	%N	%Cl	Δ_M ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹	ν_{max} (e) cm ⁻¹
[Co(bigH)(tn) ₂]Cl ₃ ·H ₂ O	Found : 13.8 Reqd : 13.64	29.0 29.14	23.9 24.62	428	20530 (140)
[Co(pic)(tn) ₂]Cl ₂	Found : 14.5 Reqd : 14.75	17.5 17.50	17.5 17.75	228	20530 (100)
[Co(acac)(tn) ₂]Cl ₂ ·H ₂ O	Found : 14.5 Reqd : 14.94	14.8 14.18	17.8 17.98	268	20000 (115)
[Co(acan)(tn) ₂]Cl ₂ ·H ₂ O	Found : 12.3 Reqd : 12.50	14.3 14.84	14.8 15.04	230	20000 (110)
[Co(benzan)(tn) ₂]Cl ₂	Found : 11.0 Reqd : 11.44	13.9 13.57	13.7 13.76	225	20000 (115)
[Co(mal)(tn) ₂]Cl·3H ₂ O	Found : 14.5 Reqd : 14.81	13.5 14.06	9.0 8.91	96	20000 (70) 28570 (95)

^aAbbreviations : tn=trimethylenediamine, bigH=biguanide, pic=deprotonated anion of picolinic acid, acac=deprotonated anion of acetylacetone, acan=deprotonated anion of acetoacetanilide, benzan=deprotonated anion of benzoylacetanilide, mal=deprotonated anion of malonic acid.

(Amberlite IR 120) column and then titrating the eluate with 0.05N NaOH. The measured values agree well with the theoretical values.

The isolation and characterisation of other salts of the complex cations, optical resolution and chromatographic studies on the complexes are in progress. The syntheses of mixed-ligand complexes using other OO, ON and NN donor ligands are progressing and details will be reported in due course.

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Complexes of Chromyl Chloride

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CHROMYL chloride is reported to form complexes with phosphorous halides¹, amides² and titanium tetrachloride³. However, its complexes with nitrogen bases (except with pyridine⁴) have not been studied so far. The pyridine complex has also not been studied in details except the elemental analysis. The formation of complexes of chromyl chloride with nitrogen bases and some oxy-donors is being reported here.

Experimental

Chromyl chloride was prepared by the method reported by Hein and Herzog⁵. It was then repeatedly distilled and the fraction distilling at 117°/740 mm was collected.

The nitrogen bases were purified by refluxing over potassium hydroxide and were fractionally distilled. Acetylacetone and acetoacetic acid were purified by fractional distillation.

Complex Formation: Ice-cold solution of chromyl chloride in carbon tetrachloride was added dropwise to excess of ice-cold solution of the base in carbon tetrachloride. Solid product so obtained was filtered, repeatedly washed with carbon tetrachloride and dried in vacuum.

Chromium in the complexes was estimated by heating the complex to 1000-1200° and weighing the residue as Cr₂O₃. Chloride was estimated by Volhard's method.

Conductances of the complexes in N, N-dimethyl formamide were measured in a dip type cell using Toshniwal CLO1/O1 conductometer.

Infrared spectra of chromyl chloride and its complexes (as nujol mulls) were scanned on Perkin Elmer 621, double beam grating spectrophotometer using polythene plates. The mulls were prepared in a dry box.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analysis (Table 1) of the complexes reveals that all the adducts of nitrogen bases with chromyl chloride bear 2:1 stoichiometry whereas those of oxydonors (acetylacetone and acetoacetic acid bear 1:1 stoichiometry to chromyl chloride. All the complexes are solids at room temperature, sensitive to traces of moisture and stable only in dry atmosphere. The complexes are insoluble in most of the common organic solvents except in N,N-dimethyl formamide in which they exhibit low solubility. The molecular weights of the complexes could not be determined due to their insolubility in the solvents having convenient freezing points.

Molar conductance data of the complexes in N,N-dimethyl formamide (Table 1) reveal that all the complexes are non-ionic in nature.

TABLE-1
PHYSICAL PROPERTIES AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES OF CHROMYL CHLORIDE

Complex	Colour	m.p.(°C)	Molar conductance (Ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹)	% of Cr		% of Cl	
				Found	Calculated	Found	Calculated
CrO ₂ Cl ₂ .2C ₂ H ₅ N	Dark brown	159	8	16.2	16.6	22.5	22.7
CrO ₂ Cl ₂ .2C ₂ H ₅ N	Light brown	Decomposes	6	15.8	16.0	22.2	21.9
CrO ₂ Cl ₂ .2C ₂ H ₅ N	Reddish brown	165	9	12.7	12.6	17.0	17.2
CrO ₂ Cl ₂ .2C ₂ H ₅ N	Brown	Above 350	5	12.8	13.1	17.7	17.9
CrO ₂ Cl ₂ .C ₄ H ₈ O ₂	Greenish brown	—do—	4	19.9	20.4	27.9	27.8
CrO ₂ Cl ₂ .C ₄ H ₈ O ₂	Light brown	—do—	5	20.3	20.2	27.8	27.6